

Feasibility study of fuel cell powered forklift truck

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This paper describes a hybrid system of PEM FC forklifts that use PEM fuel cells and a battery as a source of electricity. Hybrid systems consist of a fuel cell system, which is the primary energy source, and an energy storage system, i.e. a battery, which provides an additional source of electricity or power. The complete hybrid drive system includes a hydrogen supply system, a PEM fuel cells stack and its regulator, a DC voltage regulator, a battery, an energy management regulator, and the forklift itself. Based on the conducted techno-economic analysis, and the comparison of battery electric forklifts and forklifts with PEM fuel cells, it is shown that despite high capital costs, the use of forklifts with PEM fuel cells can reduce the total cost of ownership by 10%. Fuel-powered forklifts can reduce charging costs by up to 80% and require 75% less space compared to battery charging infrastructure. In addition, fuel cells provide constant power during shifts, while battery performance deteriorates in line with SOC reduction. Thanks to proven performance, short refueling time and the potential to increase productivity, fuel cells can compete with life-cycle batteries.

Figure 1: Hybrid forklift configuration diagram.

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Full professor at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Mechanical Engineering and Naval Architecture, University of Split. Chair of Heat Engines. Head of Laboratory for Heat Engines. Researcher has years-long experience with heat engines and implementing new technology in engine diagnostic. He is author of lots paper which deals with hybrid energy systems, expert systems, testing, diagnosing and optimization. Researcher introduced a new systems of monitoring and controlling engine. Researcher participated on several international Scientific projects.

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